

A LITERATURE REVIEW AND FUTURE INQUIRY FOR EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ENTREPRENEURIAL TEAM SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews and synthesizes the literature on emotional intelligence and team performance. As a result, we suggest an inquiry into emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial team success. Given the high failure rate associated with starting a small business and the need for team structure within entrepreneurial ventures, research on the influence of entrepreneur team success based on emotional intelligence is absent in the literature.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Entrepreneurial Team, Entrepreneurial Success, Team Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Included herein is a review of emotional intelligence models from leading theorists. To conduct a comprehensive literature review, we used a manual scan of leading business and psychology journals, as well as journals in related fields, and a web-based search of the relevant terms (e.g., emotional intelligence, team performance, entrepreneurship performance, entrepreneurial success) using several databases (e.g., Business Source Ultimate, PsycINFO, Web of Science, Google Scholar), and a scan of the references from the articles identified. The search for “emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial performance” and “emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial success” yielded no studies on emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial team performance or success.

2. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Three primary constructs define and measure contemporary emotional intelligence (Spielberger, 2004). The first, the Salovey and Mayer model (1990) described emotional intelligence as “abilities to perceive, appraise, and express emotion; to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; to understand emotion and emotional knowledge; and to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth” (Mayer and Salovey, 1997, p. 10). The second is the Boyatzis, Goleman, and Rhee model (2000), which identified a descriptive definition as, “emotional intelligence is observed when a person demonstrates the competencies that constitute self-management, social awareness, and social skills at appropriate times and ways in sufficient frequency to be effective in the situation” (Boyatzis, Goleman, and Rhee, 2000, p. 3). The third primary conceptual model is the Bar-On model (1997) that described emotional intelligence as “an array of noncognitive capabilities, competencies, and skills that influence one’s ability to succeed in coping with environmental demands and pressures” (Bar-On, 1997, p. 14). The definition for this model was amended as “a set of emotional and social skills that influence the way we perceive and express ourselves, develop and maintain social relationships, cope with challenges, and use emotional information in an effective and meaningful way” (MHS, 2011, p. 20).

Research in the field of emotional intelligence in organizational workplace settings has developed in the past two decades. The importance of emotional intelligence traces back to Charles Darwin (Bar-On 2006). In recent times, emotional intelligence has been brought into the mainstream as a popular concept by Goleman’s (1995) *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More than IQ*. Two theories guide research on emotional intelligence the ability-based model and the mixed model approach. The ability-based model

suggested a cognitive intelligence along the lines of intelligence quotient (IQ) (Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso, 2000). The mixed model, non-cognitive intelligence, includes emotional abilities mixed with personality, motivation, and effective disposition. Emotional competencies (Boyatzis et al., 2000) and emotional-social intelligence (ESI) (Bar-On, 1997, 2006, 2010; MHS, 2011) make up mixed model approaches.

3. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND TEAM PERFORMANCE

Emotional intelligence theory is in the hypothesis-testing stage of work-related outcomes (Cherniss, Extein, Goleman, and Weissberg, 2006). There is a need for future studies on a wide variety of human performance (Bar-On, 2006; 2010). As it relates to performance, the field of emotional intelligence has been steadily increasing in interest. This is particularly relevant to team performance in workplace settings. Successful team performance has increased in importance as teams become more common in contemporary organizations.

Findings suggest that emotional intelligence assessment can be useful in helping to select the best performers, who are most likely to be high achievers and expect successful business outcomes (Rosete and Ciarrochi, 2005). High levels of emotional intelligence from leaders and individual team members influence team functioning, with more research suggested in this area (Rapisarda, 2002). Additionally, emotional intelligence is linked to the function and performance of effective teamwork (Frye, Bennett, and Caldwell, 2006; Jonker, 2009). There is an expressed need to look more closely at emotional intelligence and its impact on team effectiveness (Frye et al., 2006; McCallin and Bamford, 2007). Additional research on emotional intelligence and team performance is becoming more important to researchers and managers of organizations as work teams become more common (Jordan and Troth, 2004). A correlation exists between emotional intelligence and work performance (Bar-On, 2006; Cherniss and Adler, 2000; Goleman, 1998; Mayer et al., 2000), without association with IQ or personality (Allen et al., 2021; Caruso, Mayer and Salovey, 2002; Rosete and Ciarrochi, 2005).

3.1. Models of Emotional Intelligence and Team Performance

The emotional competencies-based model of Boyatzis et al. (2000) contains a variety of self-managed competencies where the timing and frequency of these competencies are situationally effective (Boyatzis et al., 2000). Emotional competencies have been expanded to measure teams (Jonker, 2002), workgroups (Jordan, Ashkanasy, Härtel, and Hooper, 2002; Jordan and Troth, 2004; Jordan and Lawrence, 2009), and group norms (Druskat and Wolff, 2001; Koman and Wolff, 2008). Several studies have positively related average team emotional intelligence scores to team process outcomes (Chang, Sy, and Choi, 2012; Jordan et al., 2002; Rapisarda, 2002; Wolff, Pescosolido and Druskat, 2002).

The ability-based model of Mayer, Caruso, and Salovey's (1999) Multifactor Emotional Intelligence Scale (MEIS) was developed to evaluate emotional intelligence on teams, the Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Team (MSCEIT; Mayer, Salovey and Caruso, 2002). This model was further developed as the Workgroup Emotional Intelligence Profile (WEIP) by Jordan et al. (2002) and team role effectiveness by the Wong Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS) (Wong and Law, 2002). The ability-based model links emotions to cognition, which is the ability to manage emotions to facilitate thinking (Mayer et al., 2002).

The emotional social intelligence model EQ-i® of Bar-On (2006) framework relates to performance (MHS, 2011). Unlike the ability-based model of Mayer, Salovey and Caruso (2002), the EQ-i® is process-driven rather than outcome-driven (MHS, 2011). The EQ-i® was further developed to the EQ-i® 2.0 and is administered Multi-Health Systems.

Previous studies on emotional intelligence indicate a need to assess emotional intelligence in more diverse performance settings (Bar-On, 2006, 2010). Workplace teams currently play a vital role in contemporary business organizations. O'Boyle, Jr. et al. (2011) reported, "In almost all work settings, individuals have to

cooperate with others and do at least some group work tasks” (p. 793). A gap in the literature exists with suggestions for additional research on emotional intelligence and team workplace performance (Chang et al., 2012; Frye et al., 2006; Feyerherm and Rice, 2002), and EI with a wider variety of human performance (Bar-On, 2006).

4. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SUCCESS

The definition and measurement of entrepreneurial success range from financial, including firm performance and personal financial reward, to personal fulfillment, workplace relationships, and community impact (Wach, Stephan, and Gorgievski, 2016).

Allen et al.'s (2021) meta-analysis study comparing general mental ability and EI in entrepreneurial settings reported the size of the EI relationship was twice as large as the mental ability for entrepreneurial success. Boohene, Gyimah, and Osei (2019) found that EI had a strong and significant relationship with small to medium enterprises (SMEs). Further, Zampetakis, Belderkos, and Moustakis (2008) found a positive and significant relationship between EI and entrepreneurial behavior. Additionally, Rhee and White (2007) found that EI coordinated with entrepreneurial venture leaders. While research on EI and entrepreneurship is limited to the individual entrepreneur, studies addressing EI and entrepreneurial team success are absent from the literature.

Given that EI predicts team performance and entrepreneurial success, it is reasonable to expect that EI also predicts entrepreneurial team-level success. EI and its effect on entrepreneurial team success could be examined to provide a more precise lens on appropriate levels of emotional intelligence that may affect a positive and productive teamwork environment within an entrepreneurial setting. Building on our theorizing and this prior empirical work, we propose

Proposition 1: The EQ-i® 2.0 of EI will positively associate with entrepreneurial team success.

Proposition 2: The Wong and Law's (2002) shortened version of the Salovey and Mayer's (1990) model of EI will positively associate with entrepreneurial success.

Proposition 3: Building on Boyatzis et al.'s (2000) model of EI will positively associate with entrepreneurial team success.

5. DISCUSSION

We aimed to summarize the existing literatures on EI and entrepreneurial success and offer a line of inquiry to build on prior work. The majority of EI and entrepreneurial success has focused on the business owner's individual success. Therefore, we suggest that future studies examine the influence of EI on team-level entrepreneurial success. To guide this inquiry, we offer three testable propositions: (a) The EQ-i® 2.0 of EI will positively associate with entrepreneurial team success, (b) The Wong and Law's (2002) shortened version of the Salovey and Mayer's (1990) model of EI will positively associate with entrepreneurial success, and (c) Building on Boyatzis et al.'s (2000) model of EI will positively associate with entrepreneurial team success.

5.1 Implication for Future Research

We offer several implications for future EI and entrepreneurship research. First, we encourage researchers to investigate EI and Entrepreneurial team-level success by utilizing one of the three major models of EI. Findings from this research study will add to the body of knowledge and be relevant to scholars by expanding research on emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial success.

In addition to the specific testable propositions we put forth, we suggest that future research consider other EI models that were not identified in this review. The definition and measurement of entrepreneurial success often range to the personal preference of individual entrepreneurs. Therefore, specific measures of entrepreneurial success were not included in this review.

5.2 Practical Implications

Assessing the level of emotional and social competencies in people may be of interest to practitioners, principally as it relates to the performance and interactions between employees in workgroups. Empirical findings indicate that emotional and social intelligence can be improved in the workplace (Bar-On, 2006; 2010). Of particular interest to scholar-practitioners is the teachability and learnability of EI (Bar-On, 2006; 2010). Research outcomes revealed that participants who received the lowest emotional intelligence scores from taking the EQ-i® pre-test made the most progress on their post-test after taking a workshop designed to increase the level of emotional intelligence skills (Bar-On, 2010; Sjölund and Gustafsson, 2001).

Incorporating elevated levels of emotional intelligence in a workgroup environment may improve the team function and contribute to successful organizational outcomes. Developing prominent levels of emotional intelligence within a group or team structure can be learned (Bar-On, 2006, 2010; Dulewicz and Higgs, 2004; Sjölund and Gustafsson, 2001). Entrepreneurial organizations may benefit by embracing and integrating emotional intelligence and training emotional intelligence into the team-building exercises. Knowing one's level of emotional intelligence is the first step to increasing the level of emotional intelligence in order to improve performance (Bar-On, 2010).

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the review of the related literature suggests that more research on emotional intelligence and entrepreneurial success is needed. Contemporary entrepreneurial ventures seek to develop improved team-based structure dynamics to enhance success. There have been many instruments designed to assess emotional intelligence from varying constructs. We encourage future research to consider any of the models on EI to measure entrepreneurial team success.

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